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STRUCTURES AND ADAPTATIONS TO FOSTER STUDENT SUCCESS IN THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Due to the coronavirus pandemic, all engineering courses at University of the Pacific were offered in an online modality during the Fall 2020 semester. The learning environment for students in social isolation is a challenging one; studies show that social isolation can cause negative psychological effects which can adversely affect academic performance. The online medium also offers challenges related to keeping students engaged while delivering content and administering examinations in the absence of proctoring resources. Synchronous class meetings to give students a structured schedule, use of breakout rooms to help students connect with each another, use of a tablet PC with ink annotation of skeleton notes to keep students engaged during class meetings, and changes in the design of exams (to help assess student knowledge without the bias caused by access to text and online resources) are some of the structures and adaptations employed to foster student success in this challenging environment.

A comparison of student performance between the Fall 2019 in-person offering and the Fall 2020 online offering of an introductory Digital Signal Processing course was done to evaluate whether the adaptations helped to combat the negative effects of social isolation on academic performance, and the availability of resources during exams that might artificially boost exam scores. Hypothesis testing showed that the adaptations helped accomplish both objectives: an independent samples t test performed to compare the mean composite student scores of the two groups showed no statistically significant differences ($p = 0.77$) between the population means.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 The effect of the Covid-19 pandemic on the learning environment

The COVID-19 pandemic forced all classes at University of the Pacific during Fall 2020 to be conducted online. Student learning environments were altered: students could not network, socialize, or engage in group study as they previously had while on campus. They had to retreat to their individual homes and take classes remotely, in some cases being hampered by lack of suitable study spaces, easy access to software, and poor network connectivity. The pandemic has subjected students to increased levels of stress, anxiety, and depression due to factors such as loss of family income, housing instability, worry about getting infected, and anxiety about academic performance [1,2]. Studies have also indicated that learning online in the pandemic environment has had a negative effect on academic performance of students [3,4].

University of the Pacific is a private institution that prides itself on excellence in undergraduate education and meeting the needs of students. To help maintain a sense of community, foster interaction between faculty and students, lessen feelings of social isolation, and provide a structured schedule for students, the university recommended the synchronous online teaching method; classes would meet regularly online (via Zoom or Webex) at scheduled days and times. Class sessions were recorded to give students the flexibility to miss class meetings in case of emergencies. Synchronous class meetings represent the foundational structure employed to minimize the negative social effects of the pandemic. The author employed additional structures and adaptations to keep students engaged in the online learning environment and to minimize the pandemic's negative effects on academic performance: these structures and adaptations are described in the following subsections.

A study was conducted to compare the academic performance of students in the Fall 2019 offering (pre-pandemic, in-person class meetings) and the Fall 2020 offering (during pandemic, online class meetings) of a Digital Signal Processing course. The aim of the study was to evaluate whether the structures and interventions employed to minimize the negative effects of the pandemic on academic performance were successful. An independent samples t test comparing the mean composite scores of the two groups showed that there was no statistically significant differences between them: the interventions have proved to be effective at stemming loss in student academic performance in the pandemic learning environment.

1.2 Structures that helped facilitate student interaction and engagement

The backbone of the transition to online learning in response to the pandemic was the use of synchronous learning: faculty and students interacted in the virtual classroom via Zoom thrice a week at scheduled times. Asynchronous learning during a period of social isolation is difficult on students – they must have the intrinsic drive to watch video lectures, do homework, and keep in step with all their classes. The structure provided by synchronous class meetings can help students

during a period of social isolation (they can interact with their teacher and classmates) and make progress with course material just by attending class on a predictable schedule. Synchronous learning also facilitates collaboration between students.

Another structure that helped facilitate online teaching and learning was the use of skeleton notes for instruction. As can be seen in Fig. 1, the skeleton note is a file (provided ahead of time to students) containing printed text and background material with gaps in it; the gaps are filled in by the instructor during class using digital ink. The background material, problem statements and figures in the skeleton notes obviate the need for students to stay busy copying down everything that is done during class. Students instead engage with the material in class while filling in the gaps or solving problems whose statements are available in the note packet. This contrasts with one-sided PowerPoint style lectures where the all the material is in the handout and students just listen as the instructor talks through the material. Skeleton notes help keep the students engaged during class and free up time that can be used for active problem solving. Time available for active learning (which can be instructor led while the class works on solving a problem, or in breakout rooms where students feel free to come on camera and interact with each other) is the key benefit that the skeleton notes provide. Active learning and peer interaction have been shown to improve student outcomes in an online learning environment [4].

Exponentials as eigenfunctions of LTI systems

Property: Consider *any* stable LTI system having impulse response $h(n)$. The exponential signal $x(n) = z^n$ is an eigenfunction of the system with eigenvalue

$$H(z) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} h(n)z^{-n} \quad (13)$$

Note: z can be real or complex-valued. $H(z)$ is called the system transfer function.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \rightarrow y(n) &= x(n) * h(n) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} h(m)x(n-m) \\ y(n) &= \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} h(m) z^{n-m} = z^n \underbrace{\sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} h(m) z^{-m}}_{H(z)} \\ \Rightarrow y(n) &= H(z) z^n \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 1. A sample skeleton note

The final structure that helped foster communication between students and provide access to teaching assistants was the channel-based messaging platform Slack.

The Electrical and Computer Engineering department set up Slack channels for each individual class, allowing students in the class to communicate and collaborate with each other without having to exchange email addresses. All the teaching assistants in the department had a common Slack channel through which students could ask questions or join the office hours of any teaching assistant.

1.3 Adaptations employed in the pandemic environment

In the pre-pandemic environment (Fall 2019), the digital signal processing course had eight exams on theoretical concepts and one practical examination pertaining to the use of Matlab for signal processing. Having eight exams over a fifteen-week semester helps keep students abreast of the material; they cannot afford to delay engaging seriously with the course material as might be possible in a course with three examinations.

The first adaptation made in the pandemic environment (Fall 2020) was the addition of eight pre-quizzes. The quizzes were concept-based multiple choice questions that students could work on outside of class that were automatically graded by the Canvas online learning platform. Fig. 2 depicts a sample quiz question: a typical quiz had three short questions. The pre-quizzes fell roughly in the weeks where there were no scheduled exams and thus provided even more structured engagement with the course material for students. They also served to help students come to class comprehending recently presented material and prepared for the new material that was to be introduced.

Question 3	1 pts
What is the frequency (expressed in cycles/sample) of the signal $x(n) = \cos\left(\frac{2\pi n}{5} + \frac{\pi}{4}\right)$? Express your answer as a decimal number.	
<input type="text"/>	

Fig. 2. A sample quiz question

The second adaptation pertained to modification of the exam structure for the course given that our department chose to avoid the costs needed to use proctored exam services. The exams (which students took in their homes) essentially became open-book exams and therefore had to be restructured. Six out of the eight course exams were split into two parts, part A involving theory, and part B involving the use of Matlab to solve problems. The theory-based part A exams were to be completed in a short time frame, thus denying students the luxury of searching out materials from their class notes. Students had to be well prepared for the exams to be able to complete and upload them in the available time. The Matlab-based part B exams replaced the single practical exam that was employed pre-pandemic. The new model gave students many more opportunities for testing in Matlab (and thus to gain experience with this tool) than in the pre-pandemic environment. There was no time pressure for the part B exams; students had close to 12 hours to complete them. Fig. 3 depicts a sample part A exam, which students had to complete and upload in

a short time frame of 16 minutes. Fig. 4 depicts the corresponding part B exam which involves the use of Matlab for filter design and analysis.

Mini Exam 6A (12 pts total)

- (4pts) The pole-zero plot of a digital filter is depicted below. Use a geometric approach to determine the magnitude response (gain) of the filter at the frequency $\theta = \pi/2$ rad/sample. Show all your work.

- (4 pts) The transfer function of a stable, causal digital filter is $H(z) = \frac{z^2 - 2z}{z^2 - 1.4z + 0.49}$. Obtain the difference equation that can be used to implement the filter.
- (4 pts) A DSP system operates at a sampling rate of 10000 samples/sec. A digital filter is desired that will reject the $F = 2\text{kHz}$ component in the input signal. Specify the desired filter zeros needed to accomplish this; express your answer in polar form.

Fig. 3. A sample 'part A' exam with short time-constraints

Exam 6B (13 points)

Use Matlab/sptool to help design a stable, causal, bandpass filter for use in a system operating at a sampling rate of 16,000 samples/sec. The filter must have a **maximum gain of 1 at $F = 6\text{kHz}$** and must have **zero gain at both $F = 0$ and $F = 8\text{kHz}$** .

- Sketch the pole-zero plot of the filter.
- Determine the transfer function of your filter. Provide details on how you get the transfer function.
- Use Matlab to obtain the magnitude response plot of the filter you designed. The frequency axis in the plot must be in units of kHz. Place a marker at the point on the plot where the filter gain is maximum. Include a screenshot of the filter gain in your submission.

Fig. 4. A sample 'part B' exam involving use of Matlab

2 METHODOLOGY

The purpose of the study is to examine whether the interventions made in the Fall 2020 offering of the Digital Signal Processing course in the pandemic environment (F20P class) helped to prevent decline in student performance when compared with the Fall 2019 offering in a pre-pandemic environment (F19 class). All undergraduate students in the Electrical and Computer Engineering Department take the Digital Signal Processing (DSP) course, normally in their fifth semester or later. The population of students in the class thus reflects the average student population

entering the department, and can be assumed to be randomized from semester to semester.

The F19 class had 23 students with an average class grade-point-average (GPA) of 3.21 at the time of entering the DSP class. Two students were excluded from consideration in the F20P class; a student who received an F grade due to cheating, and a graduate student taking the class to fulfill prerequisites requirements. The F20P class had 18 undergraduate students after the exclusions, with an incoming average class GPA of 3.15. The incoming GPAs of 3.21 and 3.15 for the F19 and F20P student groups are very similar, supporting the premise that the population of students in the DSP class each year is a random sample of the incoming student population.

The dependent variable in the study is the final weighted student score for the class. The final weighted score is a weighted sum of scores from all assessment categories such as homework, laboratory work, and exams. In the absence of any interventions, the literature would suggest that the pandemic learning environment would cause a decline in performance of the F20P class relative to the F19P class. The study uses hypothesis testing to examine whether the interventions employed during the pandemic in the F20P class arrested any decline in performance with respect to the F19 class.

The study also examined student ratings of the DSP course and instructor in the F19 and F20P classes to see if the pandemic caused significant changes in student perceptions regarding the course and the effectiveness of the instructor.

3 RESULTS

Table 1 contains statistics pertaining to the final weighted student score for the F19 (pre-pandemic, in-person) class and the F20P (pandemic, online modality) class. A first look at the data shows that the mean student scores for the F19 and F20P are very similar; the mean for the F20P class is 0.8 points higher than the F19 class, but this difference is partly due to the deletion of a poorly performing student for cheating. The standard deviation, median, and range of the two groups are quite similar as well. The fact that the statistics of the two student groups are very similar indicates that the structures and adaptations employed during the pandemic helped prevent any decline in student performance.

Table 1. Statistics of the final weighted student score for F19 and F20P classes

	Number of students	Mean	Standard Deviation	Median	Range
Fall 19 class	23	81.2	8.4	81.9	31.7
Fall 20 class	18	82.0	9.0	81.4	31.4

A Shapiro-Wilk test supported the hypothesis that the student scores in the F19 and F20P classes were normally distributed (for F19, $W(23) = 0.93, p = 0.09$, and for

F20P, $W(18) = 0.97, p = 0.74$.) An independent-samples t-test performed to compare the mean composite student scores of the F19 and F20P classes showed no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.77$) between the groups. Results from Bartlett's test support the null hypothesis that the variances of the F19 and F20P classes are the same: $B(1) = 0.08, p = 0.77, B = 0.08 < \chi^2(3.84)$. Hypothesis testing lets us conclude that there is no statistically significant difference in the performance (mean and variance) of students in the F20P pandemic-section and the pre-pandemic F19 section, thus validating the effectiveness of the instructional structures and interventions at preventing decline in student performance due to the pressures of the pandemic. The results also show that the strategy of administering exams with short time constraints during the pandemic helped prevent increases in student grades due to availability of reference materials and unauthorized student collaboration (since the tests were unproctored.)

A study of student course evaluations was also performed to analyze student perceptions of the F19 and F20P DSP classes (students can provide anonymous feedback on the course and the performance of the instructor at the end of each semester.) The evaluation instrument has 11 categories in which students can provide feedback on the course, and 15 categories in which students can provide feedback on the performance of the instructor. Students provide responses to each category using a 5-point Likert scale, with a 1 corresponding to a poor rating, and a 5 corresponding to an outstanding rating. Example categories for course ratings include course organization, and effectiveness of class time, while example categories for instructor performance include preparedness, and availability outside of class hours. The percentages of students completing the evaluation instrument were 52.2% and 78.9% for the F19 and F20P classes, respectively. Due to the difference in response rate, student rating medians were examined rather than the means, as the median inherently filters out extreme responses.

Table 2 contains data on categories for which the median ratings for the F19 and F20P classes were different. The drop in student ratings in the course category were in areas where course changes were made in the F20P class, namely the addition of extra quizzes, and the reduction in time available for part A exams. The results of this study show that the exam changes helped prevent score increases that could be associated with unauthorized student collaboration during exams. Gaining this outcome at the expense of a small drop in student rating is an acceptable tradeoff.

The drop in median student rating from 5 to 4 in the instructor category were in areas related to level of enthusiasm for the subject, and ability to keep students interested / motivated. This drop in rating is not surprising given the transition from in-person to online learning: it is a lot more difficult to convey enthusiasm and keep students interested and motivated in an online modality.

Table 2. Categories in which median rating changed between F19 and F20P classes

Rating category	Median student rating	
	F19 class	F20P class
Course: Quality of tests and quizzes as measures of achievement	5	4
Course: Appropriateness of number of tests, quizzes	5	4
Instructor: Level of enthusiasm for subject	5	4
Instructor: Ability to keep students interested / motivated; conveys relevance of course	5	4

Out of 26 categories in which students could rate the course and the instructor, the median ratings between the F19 and F20P classes were different only in four categories. In these categories the median rating dropped from 5 (Outstanding) to Very Good (4). This leads to the conclusion that student satisfaction with the course and the instructor was substantially the same in the F19 and F20P semesters. This is remarkable given that the F19 class was offered in person while the F20P class was online with social isolation. The teaching structures and adaptations employed in the pandemic environment have kept student perceptions on the quality of the course and the instructor relatively unchanged between the pre-pandemic and pandemic environments. This conclusion is also supported by written student comments in the course evaluations. There were comments indicating that the DSP class was well suited for online delivery and that the remote version went very well. Two students made positive comments regarding synchronous class meetings. The F20P course had more written comments commending the instructor's teaching style and course organization than the F19 course.

REFERENCES

- [1] Son, C., Hegde, S., Smith, A., Wang, X., and Sasangohar, F. (2020), Effects of COVID-19 on College Students' Mental Health in the United States: Interview Survey Study, *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, Vol. 22, No. 9. <https://doi.org/10.2196/21279>
- [2] The impact of COVID-19 on college student well-being: Healthy Minds Network / American College Health Association Report, https://healthymindsnetwork.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Healthy_Minds_NCHA_COVID_Survey_Report_FINAL.p
- [3] Aucejo, E., French, J., Araya, M., and Zafar, B. (2020), The impact of COVID-19 on student experiences and expectations: Evidence from a survey, *Journal of Public Economics*, Vol. 191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2020.104271>
- [4] McDougall, A., Orlov, G., and McKee, D. (2020), Learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, <https://voxeu.org/article/learning-during-covid-19-pandemic>